

STRESS AND BURNOUT AMONG PRESERVICE TEACHERS' SUPERVISORS: A SCOPING REVIEW

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Abstract

Several studies by internationally acclaimed researchers had confirmed that teachers continue to experience stress and burnout, which threaten the monitoring of preservice teachers during their teaching practice. Some of the reasons attributed to this include the increase in the supervision workload among teachers, lack of self-care, and lack of resources, among others. Although few studies had investigated how teachers experience different forms of stress at different levels, some of them failed to identify the forms and causes of stress and burnout among preservice teachers' supervisors, who themselves are teachers. On this note, this scoping review aimed at reporting the emerging evidence on stress and burnout among preservice teachers' supervisors. The researcher searched through ERIC, EBSCO, SciELO, SCOPUS, MEDLINE (Database of the Medical Literature Analysis and Retrieval System) and APA (PsycINFO on Allied Health Literature). A comprehensive literature search was carried out from January to March 2025 on stress and burnout among preservice teachers' supervisors. Fifteen studies met the following criteria: (a) focused on stress and burnout (SB); (b) The prevalence of stress among preservice teacher' supervisors; (c) Prevalence of burnout among teachers and preservice teachers' supervisors, (f) published articles from the period 2014-2024. The included studies met the quality control standards for Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and meta-analysis and Scoping review (PRISMA-Scr). The outcome of the study reveals that of the 11,141 participants reported by the scoping review (15 articles), 3,733 participants, which is 33.5%, show that there are stress and burnout among teachers in Turkey. Moreover, 4,117 participants from Spain, which is equivalent to 37% of the whole countries exhibit stress as well. The trending evidence that endorses the result of the study shows that there is stress and burnout among teachers even around the world.

Keywords: Stress, burnout, teachers, supervisors, preservice teachers, database

1. Introduction

Recently, some internationally acclaimed researchers had reported that stress and burnout among teachers, pre-service teachers, and their supervisors are taking a high toll on teachers' health, due to the high demand of a workload assigned by school administrators to appointed teachers for given teaching practice supervision, classroom teaching, student monitoring, and community service, among many others. (Agyapong et al., 2022a; Fernández-García et al., 2024; Hazan-Liran & Karni-Vizer., 2024; Hongsa & Polyong., 2024; Ma et al., 2022; Yang et al., 2025). According to Clipa and Boghean (2015) and Clipa (2016), they emphasised that crucial roles of teachers in our different environments cannot be overemphasized, because they facilitate processes teaching and learning which be of help to the students in educating our pupils to be fitted for the community. But the fact remains that some pre-service teacher supervisors who are themselves teachers face some serious challenges when trying to complete their assignment in monitoring teachers to come. Due to the nature of their work and the high workload assigned to them, some supervisors often experienced different levels of stress and burnout, which affect the monitoring and support process of aspiring teachers as they transition from theory to practice (Öztürk, 2021). However, this critical role comes with inherent stressors that could significantly affect the supervisor's well-being and effectiveness due to a high workload as reported in the National Education Association (NEA) with a heart-breaking report on teachers stress and burnout (NEA, 2022; Yang et al., 2025).

A recent publication had indicated that the stress among supervisors was reported with the following statistical data indicated below; Clipa report that some sources of stress include the fear of insecurity (6,7%), while pressure (28 %), uncertainty (10%), frustration (6%), threat (13%), constraint (9%) and requirement (39%) among many

others had contributed to stress among pre-service teachers supervisors (Agyapong et al., 2022; Clipa, 2017).). From the data presented, it could be noticed that most teachers associate professional stress to some conditions like pressure and uncertainty. Therefore, a study by Delvin, in a recent survey proposes that in 2025, 48% of educators are planning to leave the field of teaching and monitoring the preservice teachers due to the poor compensation given to them by their employers, while 42% have already left because of the same reason. On the aspect of expectations, 33% plan on leaving, while 31% had left for this reason. Based on this, teachers' well-being and health report show that (31%/23%) will be leaving the profession, while the stress from the leadership may pull out 30%/31%, and lack of workplace flexibility and stress 26%/21% may be quitting (Delvin, 2025). At the same time, 58% will stay because of meaningful work, 39% because of their co-workers, 34% because of compensation, 28% because of geography and 27% because of community. Similarly, Agyapong and others recently reported that the conditions of stress and burnout among teachers are becoming alarming, and if care is not taken, these prevalence factors may lead to total burnout and psychological disturbance among teachers. They further reported that there is a prevalence of burnout and stress among some teachers, which ranges from 25.12% to 74% burnout rate, and the stress among teachers ranged from 8.3% to 87.1%, anxiety among them ranged from 38% to 41.2%, and depression ranged from 4% to 77% (Agyapong et al., 2022a).). Going by the crucial statistical reports stated above, it could be said that workplace stress and burnout had remained one of the major reasons, while many in-service teachers, preservice teachers, and their supervisors are planning to quite the teaching profession as generally specified by the above-mentioned researchers. It is on this note that this study had resolved to review the multifaceted nature of stress experienced by teachers and teachers' supervisors in preparation for the classroom using scoping review.

For a better understanding of the study, the researchers described stress as a complex interplay of psychological and behavioral responses to perceived demands that exceed an individual's perceived capacity to cope (Agyapong et al., 2022; Ahmad et al., 2025). For teachers and supervisors, there are several demands that arise in various classrooms when monitoring preservice teachers. And some of the causes of stress include the job and organizational demands from the employers, high expectations from their senior teachers, challenges of balancing the need to support preservice teachers while maintaining high standards of professional practice, time constraints, combining the external supervisory role together with their own teaching or administrative duties (Hongsa & Polyong, 2024.; Lee & Lai, 2020). Furthermore, some researchers also argue that some additional issues, such as administrative work, personal requests from students for assistance, and some administrative demand, also result in overwork and burnout among supervisors (Kamal, 2021). However, the fact remains that all these challenges cannot be addressed without identifying whether there is stress and burnout or not. Therefore, this study reviews some of the main aspects of stress and burnout among teachers, which will serve as a pivotal to resolve the problems identified among teachers and to understand the tools available used among experts to measure different forms of stress and burnout among teachers.

1.1 Stress and burnout among teachers in schools

Several researchers had described stress as a particular interaction between a person and his/her environment, which the person assesses or evaluates as being taxing or exceeding his or her personal resources due to some participation in some modern activities as a teacher (Aderibigbe et al., 2020; Czuba et al., 2019). Thus, disrupting his or her daily routines and, if not well managed, may lead to psychological disturbance and burnout (Lee & Lai, 2020; Montgomery & Rupp, 2005). According to Wettstein et al. (2021), stress is a state of psychological pressure and disorder found among teachers due to their heavy occupational activities. And some of the sources of stress are personality mediators that include constructs of time pressure and behaviour, the subjective nature of an individual, biological factors and environmental factors that include constructs of vocational satisfaction and domestic satisfaction, and emotional responses that also include constructs of hostility, anxiety, and depression. There are different sources of stress as reported by some researchers, such as teacher stress and other job-related stress (Aderibigbe et al., 2020). However, some researchers, teachers, unanimously identified classroom disruptions as the main stress factor that contributes to stress and burnout in an empirical study carried out by some researchers (Wettstein et al., 2021). These sources of stress could be classified into long- and short-term psychosocial stressors, which are found among students and teachers, and this always negatively affects the teaching and learning process (Aldrup et al., 2017; Chen et al., 2025). Short-term stress can lead to long-term stress, leading to early dropouts from the profession and high health costs and demand (Wettstein et al., 2021). However, it is still unclear under what conditions disruptions occur in the classroom that trigger acute psychological and physiological stress reactions among teachers (Wettstein et al., 2020), but the fact remains that stress among teachers could be detected using different instruments; this includes ambulatory assessment (AA), which helps in measuring stress among teachers by asking them to report on their experiences as they go about

their daily teaching activities (Wettstein et al., 2020). Based on the available literature, one could argue that work discontent, work overload, pressure to succeed, excessive demands, social surcharge, social tensions, social isolation, lack of social recognition, family issues and chronic worry could be considered as some of the major stressors of stress among teachers of all categories (Aderibigbe et al., 2020; Padillo et al., 2024; Wettstein et al., 2020).

On the other hand, burnout is a stress-related problem for the individual who works in interpersonally orientated occupations such as healthcare and education (Nil et al., 2010; Maslach & Leiter, 2024). Similarly, Skaalvik and Skaalvik (2020) carefully describe burnout among pre-service teachers' supervisors as high-level stress that can result from excessive demands on their energy, strength, and resources. Therefore, one could argue that there is an interrelationship between increasing evidence that burnout is a negative stress response that represents a risk factor not only for depression, but also for cardiovascular and other somatic diseases (Aderibigbe et al., 2020; Nil et al., 2010). On this note, burnout is a state of chronic exhaustion that could develop from prolonged stress. Stress may be a positive or negative state, but burnout is a feeling of being empty and depleted. Based on the views of some researchers, burnout could be conceptualized as having three interrelated components that include emotional exhaustion, depersonalization, and reduced personal achievement (Agyapong et al., 2022). Some researchers reported that those participants who reported high levels of anxiety could encounter some high level of stress that could increase levels of burnout. On this note, one could report that the source of a very high level of stress that could lead to burnout is workload stress (100%), anxiety (67.5%), and depression (23.2%), and all of these are common among pre-service teachers' supervisors (Agyapong et al., 2022; Skaalvik & Skaalvik, 2020). A high level of stress found among teachers of different categories could be associated with the teaching professional, which are overlapping issues, such as burnout, anxiety, and depression. All these are myriads that affect the performance of teachers' health, well-being, and productivity (Agyapong, 2022).

1.2 Current study

The researcher sought to explore some available studies on common stressors and burnout among teachers in schools. To achieve the objectives and objectives of this study, the following research questions were used as a guide for the study.

- What are the prevalences of stress and burnout among preservice teachers' supervisors?
- How are these stressors measured among pre-service teachers' supervisors?

All of these were done to understand the recent state of stress and burnout among teachers and to propose a way forward.

2. Method

2.1. Research Design:

The scoping review identified emerging issues and studied the impact of stress and burnout among teachers due to the high workload among them (Agyapong et al., 2022a; Fernández-García et al., 2024; Hazan-Liran & Karni-Vizer., 2024). Furthermore, these scoping reviews were conducted to report the state of stress and burnout in teachers' health and how to identify the forms of stress and burnout among teachers. This was done to report an overview of emerging evidence by methodological quality or risk of bias since studies on stress and burnout using an explanatory report (Udoh et al., 2023). Therefore, scoping review became the appropriate means of reporting the broad version of stress among teachers.

2.2. Search Procedure:

For the data collection procedure, the researcher adopts a comprehensive search strategy that allows for replicability, reliability, and transparency. Therefore, to achieve a high level of precision, this scoping review followed Arksey and O'Malley's five-stage approach to scoping reviews: identifying the research question, searching for relevant studies, study selection, charting the data and collating, summarizing and reporting the results (Arksey, 2005; Tricco et al., 2018). To achieve this, the researcher worked closely with the librarian who helps the data search process by using her expertise knowledge on the database available on the university of South Africa's library website.

Table 1: The literature reviews key topics and search terms

Key concepts	Searches
Stress OR teacher	"Stress among teachers" OR "occupational stress" "High level stress" OR "overwork" OR "poor stress management".

Stress AND anxiety among teachers	“Stress among teachers” AND “anxiety among teachers” AND “Stress”. High workload, schools, school stress, school job dissatisfaction
Stress AND its management among teachers	“Stress” AND “stress management among teachers”
Burnout OR teacher	Burnout among teachers” Or “worn-out”
Burnout AND Worn-out	Mental disorder and stress in schools, form of stress
occupational burnout OR stress among teachers;	AB (stress and burnout among teachers) AND TX stress management among teachers OR (stress and anxiety among teachers) AND (burnout or burnout or burnout or stress or occupational stress among teachers).

2.3 Information sources and identification of relevant studies

The search was carried out using relevant terms to identify and select articles in the following databases: ERIC, EBSCO, sciELO SCOPUS, MEDLINE (Database of the Medical Literature Analysis and Retrieval System) and APA (PsycINFO on Allied Health Literature). The researcher carried out a comprehensive literature search in January – March 2025. Five academic databases were searched to identify relevant studies. Academic Search Premier, Eric, PsycInfo, Scopus, and EBSCO. The researcher adopts some keywords and their synonyms to identify all relevant studies using an appropriate data base AB (stress and burnout among teachers) AND TX stress management among teachers OR (stress and anxiety among teachers) AND (burnout or burnout or burnout or stress or occupational stress among teachers).The author conducted a supplementary search on Google Scholar and searched the reference list of the relevant studies identified in the key databases to ensure that all eligible studies were included.

Table 2: Summary of eligibility conditions

Variables	Inclusion	Exclusion
Study design	Qualitative, mixed method, quantitative and peer reviewed	Case study, review papers, and editor’s note
Publication year	2014	2024
Participants	Teachers, preservice teachers, preservice teachers’ supervisor	Preservice teachers
Intervention	Identification of Self-reports	Identification through observation
Outcomes	Stress and burnout are common among preservice teacher’ supervisors	Student’ stress was not included in the study

2. 4. Inclusion/exclusion criteria

To obtain an accurate study suitable for this scoping review, the researcher included all empirical studies on stress and burnout among teachers for the last 10 years (2014-2024), and this was done using the mixed method and qualitative approach. Further condition for inclusive and exclusive criteria were hereby reported in table 2. This method of selecting the literature helps to report the stress and burnout among the preservice teachers around the world.

The researcher screened all studies identified through the database search according to the eligibility criteria. The screening was carried out in three stages. First, the titles were carefully searched and identified with a mind of selecting the relevant topics on stress and burnout among teachers, two, the abstracts of the articles were screened to identify studies that potentially met the criteria. Three, the full texts of the articles that potentially met the criteria were examined in detail to identify the studies that met all the eligibility criteria. All included studies were cross-checked by the researcher to ensure eligibility. It is important to note that all the Studies that were not written in were excluded (see table 3).

2.5 Data extraction

The researcher extracted data using a database descriptor and Google scholar by downloading and reading each paper one after the other by going through the abstract and the conclusion section. The data extracted included the details of the authors, country, sample size, study design, group of participants, number of

participants, prevalence concepts, measurement tools and the outcome of each study. All these were made possible using University of South Africa library site.

Table 3: Summary of the study’s participants and their common characteristics of the included studies

Author/ year	Country	Study design	Sample size	Participants	Measurement scale	Prevalence concepts/comm on stressors	Key findings/outcom es show(s) that;
1. Akin (2019)	Turkey	Cross-sectional	3478	Teachers	Maslach burnout inventory,	Emotional exhaustion, depersonalisation, and burnout	Stress and burnout depend on the gender status among the teachers.
2.. Boshoff et al. (2014)	South Africa	Cross sectional survey	200	Teachers	Teacher Stress Inventory (Self-report)	Stress, depression, burnout, and anxiety	There are some levels of stress among teachers in South Africa.
3. Capone and Petrillo (2018)	Italy	Cross sectional	285	Teachers	self-report questionnaire,	Depression, burnout, stress, and mental health	Job satisfaction reduces stress and burnout.
4. Clipa (2017)	Romania	Cross-sectional	120	Teachers	Professional Stress Perception Questionnaire	Stress, burnout, frustration, pressure, threat, constrain, and uncertainty	The ways to cope with stress include a positive organisational environment and a better working environment.
5. Fernández-Garca et al. (2024)	Spain	Cross sectional survey	4117	Teachers	Self-report	Stress, anxiety, and burnout.	The conclusion is that being physically active helps reduce the effect of disruptive states on well-being.
6. Hazan-Liran and Karni-Vizer (2024)	Israel	Cross sectional	123	Teachers	Questionnaire (self-report)	Stress, anxiety, and burnout	The need to rethink working conditions for teachers in standard education when classes are required to be inclusive.
7. Hongsa, and Polyong (2024).	Thailand	Cross sectional study	400	Teachers	Questionnaire (self-report)	Stress, burnout, stress burnout, and sleeplessness	This student confirmed that the frequent or almost constant time pressure at work increases the teacher’s stress.
8. Kamal et al. (2021)	Egypt	Cross sectional	400	Teachers	Stress, burnout, anxiety, depression,	Stress not measured.	It shows that there is a form of 100% stress among teachers and that urgent

								attention is needed.
9.	Lee and Lai (2020)	Malaysia	Cross sectional survey	150	Teachers	The Oxford Happiness Questionnaire	Stress, anxiety, depression, mental problems	The health situation of female teachers needs to be monitored to avoid total burnout.
10.	Liu et al. (2021)	China	Cross sectional	907	teachers	MBI scale, and self-report questionnaire	Depression, stress, burnout	Attention should be paid to the teachers' mental health to avoid total burnout
11.	Mathews et al. (2022).	South Africa	Mixed method	11	Preservice Teachers	Self-report questionnaire	Depression, stress, anxiety, and burnout	Stress among the preservice teachers is as a result of the university program design for the preservice teachers
12.	Méndez et al (2020)	Spain	Cross sectional	210	Teachers	Self-Rating scale, MBI,	Stress, burnout, depression, and anxiety	The results revealed that there are different categories of stress and burnout.
13.	Nwakpado lu et al. (2024)	Nigeria	Cross sectional	121	Teachers	Questionnaire (self-report)	Stress and burnout	The study confirmed that the demand of the job resulted to high demand of stress among the teachers.
14.	Oberle et al (2016)	Canada	Cross sectional	406	Teachers and students	Measurement of Cortisol in saliva	Stress, burnout, psychological stress	The level of stress among the participants varies
15.	Owusu et al, (2024)	Ghana	Cross sectional survey	312	Teachers	Questionnaire (self-report)	Stress and burnout,	This finding confirms that there are stress and burnout among the teachers in open-distance university.

2.6 Data quality

The quality of this study includes some relevant studies gathered from different sources and databases to perform this scoping reviewed using a PRISMA-ScR as adopted by some researchers on stress and burnout among the teachers (Agyapong et al., 2022). This accuracy of the data collected was made possible by the researcher by using the university's database, which assists the researcher in getting out some research papers which a peer-reviewed papers. Furthermore, the researcher adopted a checklist previously reported by the Joanna Briggs Institute when reporting their study on PRISMA ScR (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses to

Scoring Review). The checklist reported some major aspects of the study which are (title, abstract, introduction, method, result, discussion, and funding). All these were suggested by Tricco and others due to their reliability with the process of reporting the state of stress and burnout among teachers around the world using an extended and wider review approach (Agyapong et al., 2022a; Tricco et al., 2018). For better understanding the flow chart was found to be necessary since it report the process of data identification, inclusion, exclusion, and process adopted as shown below (Fatokun & Gumbo, 2024; Udoh et al., 2023).

Figure 1:
Flow chart for data collection and collation stage

2.7. Risk of bias assessment

The risk assessment of this study was done using an appraisal tool for cross-sectional study commonly known as AXIS. This was used to assess the possible methodological rigor to resolve the biases which include selection bias, performance bias, detection bias, attrition bias, reporting bias, and other bias. This risk assessment tool was found to be more appropriate assessment tool for evaluating the quality and potential bias in a cross-sectional survey design (AXIS). AXIS was developed to specifically addresses the unique characteristics of cross-sectional studies, which include their design, reporting quality, and risk. (Downes et al., 2016). AXIS serves as an evaluation tool designed to gauge both quality and potential bias in systematic reviews. It assists researchers in ensuring the literature chosen for the review process is balanced. Developed initially through Delphi methodology, it stands as the premiere critical appraisal tool available for assessing evidence for systematic decision-making (Downes et al., 2016). This was done using a sample questionnaire proposed for this purpose, therefore, AXIS had assisted the researcher in reporting the quality of this scoping review using some available data from some peer reviewed articles.

3. Findings

3.1. Data Synthesis

This result of this study was generated by identifying 115, 576 selected journal articles were gathered from different databases, of which 68, 221 were taken from academic journals, 380 were reports taken from different researchers, while 154 journal articles were magazine and 69 conference papers, 25 reviews, and 13 books. Furthermore, in obtaining more than 49 papers were critically screened by carefully reading their abstract, methodology, and the discussion section. The total of 15 journal articles selected for the study, one of them carried

out a mixed method study, while others 15 articles were reported using a cross-sectional design in conducting their studies on stress, burnout among teachers (see table 3).

Furthermore, during the process of the critical review, some major issues were commonly found repeating themselves in the process of data generation and these were positively critics as followed in line with the views of the selected authors. The 15 journal articles include a total number of 11, 141 participants were used for the study and their views were reports by the authors. Therefore, my scoping review was based on the views of each author according to their outcome. The chosen participants adopted for the study on stress among the teachers were from different institution of learning which include, primary, secondary, and the university. And the sample rate used by their study falls within 11 to 4117 participants and the articles were published within the years 2014 to 2024. It is significant to note that 67% of the articles used for this study were recently published by some researchers (Hazan-Liran & Karni-Vizer, 2024; Hongsa & Polyong, 2024; Boshoff et al., 2014). Therefore, it could be said that for the past years not many articles were published on stress and burnout among the teachers by many researchers around. On the other hand, an increase in numbers of the publication begins to increase from the last 8 years, which implies that publications on stress and burnout among the teachers were not taken serious by many researchers around the world.

From table 3, which reports the distribution of the study on stress and burnout around the world, 7% of the publication journals used by the researcher reported some aspects of stress and burnout among the teachers came in United Kingdom with 640 participants which is equivalent to 5.7% (Taylor et al., 2021). While 13% of the publications gathered by the researcher with 211 participants which equivalent to 1.9% reported their views on stress and burnout among the teachers in South Africa (Boshoff et al., 2014; Mathews et al., 2022). It is important to note that, most of the researchers from other countries do not perform well regarding their studies on stress and burnout among the teachers (see table 3 for details).

In addition to this, a glance check at the table 3 above, has shown that 99% of the participants, which is equivalent to 11, 141 participants which are predominantly teachers are of opinion that stress and burnout are commonly found among them both preservice teachers, in-service teachers and supervisors that are working with the future teachers (Mathews et al., 2022; Méndez et al., 2025; Oberle et al., 2016). Similarly, one could argue that all the journal articles selected and adopted for this scoping review speak to the stress and burnout among the teachers (see table 3).

3.2: Themes identified

This section of the study presents the critical report of the prevalent concepts that are common to stress and burnout among the preservice teachers' supervisors. And this was done under the following themes to report the common concepts (De Klerk et al., 2023).

Theme 1: The prevalence of stress among preservice teachers' supervisors

This study had reported a very high rate of stress among the teachers and the supervisors monitoring the teachers to-be (preservice teachers). Gathering from the results of the literature reviewed, it could be said that 11, 141 teachers participated in the study on stress and burnout among the teaching profession. And it is significant to noted that all these participants confirmed that they undergo different forms of stress when carrying out their professional duties (Aderibigbe et al., 2020; Akin, 2019; Boshoff et al., 2014; Capone & Petrillo, 2018; Ozturk, 2021; Paquette & Rieg, 2021). All their views as reported by the reviewed literature confirmed that the heavy workload, condition of service, poor facilities available for teachers, lack of teaching resources, poor housing facilities for teacher and lack of medical check-up and treatment among many others had contributed to their stress. Furthermore, some recently published papers from 2020 to 2025 had reported that stress among the teachers had deteriorate the level of activeness among many teachers due to a high rate of students both in high school and universities (Paquette & Rieg, 2021; Ratanasiripong et al., 2022). And high workload among the teachers could be due to non-availability of a well competent hands to support the in-service teachers.

From the journal articles reviewed, it significant to note that studies from 2014 to 2015 do not emphasised on the stress among teachers even as reported around the world. On this note, the researcher was able to trace only a study that spoke to stress among the teachers. within the range of years mentioned. As a result of this, there is a high prevalence of stress among the teachers' due lack of publications speaking to the health challenges of some teachers in schools, and this had affected their productivities in discharging their responsibilities as teachers (Capone & Petrillo, 2018). On the other hand, studies from 2016 to 2024 recorded a high rate of studies on stress among teachers and this could be linked to the high level of stress found among the teachers in recent time. And this could be linked to stress introduced by COVID 19 in recent years which eventually resulted to a high work rate of the teachers around the world due to the introduction of e-learning around the work (Fasinu, 2024; Klapproth

et al., 2020; Zito et al., 2024). This corroborates with Agyapong and others, who reported that the studies on pandemic had exposed a high rate of stress found among teachers around the world. In their study, they argued that 58.7% of teachers developed a high rate of stress in relation to work pressure, which could result to depression among the teachers (Agyanpong et al., 2022a; Wettstein et al., 2021).

In a nutshell, stress among the teachers as reported by Lee and Lai (2021), Mathews et al. (2024) and Nwakpadolu et al. (2024) could be traced to high workload, fear of pandemic, work condition, lack of administrative support, poor condition of teaching due to lack of resources and poor remuneration among many others. On this note, care should be taken by the employers to see to the above stated issues to avoid teachers' breakdown which may invariably affects their productivity and psychological health and may lead to total burnout (Li et al., 2024).

Theme 2: Prevalence of burnout among the teachers and preservice teachers' supervisors

Burnout is a high level of stress commonly found among teachers, and this could be related to an occupational overstress among the teachers which if not well managed could lead to a psychological problem that may require the assistance of some medical experts before a reasonable resolution could be attained (Agyapong et al., 2022b). Several studies had reported some of the teachers found around the world with some psychological distraction encountered as result of job-related burnout which had really affected the activities as teachers. Some of the employers don't take care of their employee health challenges therefore, forcing most of them to encounter a burnout stage of stress which at times always come some health issues like depression, pressure, and psychology health issues (Valosek et al., 2021; Wettstein et al., 2020b).

Previous studies reported in table 3 indicate that starting from year 2014, most of the reviewed journal articles do not lay much emphasis on burnout among the teachers, this may be due to the researchers' not recognising the differences between both stress and burnout. In fact, going by the table 3 report, the low appearance of burnout in the reviewed articles, indicate that it is non-appearance concepts among the published research articles. Therefore, it could be clearly seen that some researchers do not explain in detail the meaning of burnout and how it could affect both the in-service teachers, preservice teachers, and their supervisors. Thereby affecting the job-related burnout that some teachers experienced due to high level of stress that could demand urgent attention. Some importance could be attached to this psychology problem which could be found among some teachers with some extra-work-related assignment such as monitoring some teaching practice students (Boshoff et al., 2014). Similarly, previous studies do not give attention to burnout as they were neglected by most researchers. And this had generated multifaceted problem among the teachers. But recently, some studies had stood to the responsibility of identifying some aspects of teachers' health that could increase their performance in the process of teaching and learning.

Furthermore, the data gathered for these studies had shown that out of 11, 141 participants investigated for their studies, from the 15 peer reviewed papers do not report the different forms of burnout found among teachers but, the fact remain that burnout among in-service teachers and professional teacher defers, and this should be addressed to reduce the prevalence of some psychological problems among teachers. On this note, most of the articles do not report the source of burnout found among teachers which could be classified as risk to teachers and the teaching profession which remains a pivotal to the economic development of a nation. But this study had confirmed that some of causes of burnout are stress and job overload. And these include low manpower in schools, and high students' intake among many others (Boshoff et al., 2014; Liu et al., 2021; Mathews et al., 2022; Owusu et al., 2024).

In a nutshell, the report of the studies starting from year 2016 confirmed that there is a high level of burnout among teachers. As a result of this, more studies has been coming up to report the source of burnout which include workload, condition of service, and high learners' intake among many others (Klapproth et al., 2020; Skaalvik & Skaalvik, 2020; Ramberg et al., 2021; Ratanasiripong et al., 2022). All these studies had reported a high level of burnout among the teachers. The above cited studies correlate with Agyapong who argued that 70.9% of teachers experiences a high rate of burnout when teaching their students, 28.8% of the teachers were also found experiencing different forms of burnout (Agyapong et al., 2020a; 2020b; Li et al., 2024). This implies that there is a high rate of burnout among teachers all over the world.

Theme 3: Other prevalence concepts among the teachers undergoing stress and burnout

This study also reports some stressors common to teachers, preservice teachers and their supervisors when monitoring the teachers to-be. Some of these concepts common to the 15 reviewed paper are, depression, anxiety, pressure, and sleeplessness among many others (Oberle et al., 2016; Owusu et al., 2024; Öztürk, 2021; Paquette & Rieg, 2021; Pressley, 2021; Ramberg et al., 2021; Schussler et al., 2018; Skaalvik & Skaalvik, 2020).

This implies that anxiety, depression, and sleeplessness are also common to the teachers with stress and burnout as result of the job-related stress and burnout. All the articles reviewed had shown that stress and burnout are serious of psychological health issues common among the teachers, and if care is not taken by the teachers, and their employers it could lead to a permanent psychology disease.

Theme 4: Prevalence of Self-report as a stress and burnout measuring tool

The studies on stress and burnout among the teachers could not be concluded without talking about how to identify the stress and burnout among the teachers. On this note, all the participants identified by the researchers which was earlier reported as 11, 141 from different locations (14) reported in table 3, had shown that there are different forms of stress found among the teachers around the world (Aydogan et al., 2009; Boshoff et al., 2014; Oberle et al., 2016; Owusu et al., 2024; Ozturk, 2021; Pressley, 2021)

Several studies had reported the measurement of stress and burnout among the teachers, and some of the tools available in measuring stress and burnout include Self-report tool questionnaire), MBI tool, observational AA, and other biological AA tools (Agyapong et al., 2022a; 2022b; Lee & Lai, 2021; Liu et al., 2021; Mendez et al., 2025). The review of the selected 30 papers had shown that among the above-mentioned burnout measurement tools, Self- report tool had found to be the prevalence burnout measuring tool available among a high percentage of researchers (Mathews et al., 2025). Also, the MBI tool was found to be a common tool for measuring burnout among the teachers, but the fact remains that Self-report questionnaire was found as the common tool that some researchers accepted when measurement stress and burnout. Therefore, the researcher could authoritatively say that 100% of the participants adopted Self-report tools in measuring burnout among the teachers.

In a nutshell, AA could be used by as a model could assist the teachers to recognise the level of their stress as and recommend what to avoid been led to a burnout situation, it is on this note that researcher suggests that when a using a AA in clinical psychology will help to investigate mechanisms and dynamics of psychopathological symptoms, to predict treatment success, to prevent relapse, and to administer interventions.

Figure 1: A Modified AA Stress Measurement Model

Although, the model displaced above has its importance to the measurement of stress, but some key aspects of burnout could not be measured. In view of this the researchers had introduced a conceptual framework appropriate for the recognition of the stress level among the teachers.

Discussion

4.0. Findings and its implications

This study on the scoping review included 15 articles gathered from different database and were critically reviewed with intension of gathering the prevalence concepts. At the end of the review, some prevalence concepts which are common to stressors and burnout were identified and described in line with the views of the researchers (Agyapong, 2022a; 2022b; Aydogan et al., 2009; Li et al., 2024). The prevalence concepts are stress, burnout, self-report measurement tool, and other words like anxiety, depression, and sleeplessness among teachers. The review indicates that 3,733 participants which amount to 33.5% show that there are stress and burnout among teachers in Turkey. Similarly, a report gathered from Spain shows that 4,117 participants which is equivalent to 37% of the total participants of (11, 141 teachers) are under stress and burnout. While in South Africa, which represent the demographic information from South Africa shows that 2% of the study was located within the Southern Africa, which shown a serious concern for teachers in the region in Africa. The low number research identified by the researchers is a thing of serious issue for teachers in that region because, if care is not taken

some of the stressors among the teachers in this region may develop into a total burnout which could affect the psychology health of the teachers.

More so, countries like, China with the total participants of 907 (8%) teachers investigated, Thailand 400 (3.6%), Egypt 400 (3.6%), Italy with 285 (2.5%) participants report a low participant which is not good for those regions. Furthermore, when talking about the measurement of stress among teachers, majority of the articles reviewed confirmed that most of the teachers around the world are under stress and burnout. Studies gathered from some researchers show some level of stress and burnout among teachers (Clipa, 2017; Capone & Petrillo, 2018; Kamal et al., 2021; Lee & Lai, 2020; Liu, 2020; Mathews et al, 2022; Mendez et al., 2025). Report from the above cited study indicate that the stated tools below are reliable for measuring stress and burnout among which are self-report inventory, MBI and other biological approaches. But the result of this scoping review had indicated that there are high numbers of scholars who prefer using the self-report for identifying the stress and burnout among the teachers due to its cost when doing research (Agyapong et al., 2022).

4.1. Implications for Practice and further research

The findings from this scoping review suggest a need for both educational stakeholders and teachers to re-strategize their professional engagement to reduce the level of stress and burnout among them. The fact remains that if this is not done to reduce the teachers' activities and improve the process of teaching and learning, excessive workload, overlabour, and fear could lead to mental disorder and could affect teachers' productivity and may eventually impact the process of teaching and learning negatively. On this note there is a need of conducting an empirical study among preservice teachers in Africa as a continent to avoid total collapse in this sector.

4.2. Limitation of the study

This study had reported the general views of some researchers on stress among teacher around the world, but the fact remain that this study cannot be generalised due to limited research on the topic which investigate stress and burnout among teachers. And this is as result of a limited articles available to report the state of thing within some countries. For instance, much research has not been conducted in a continent like Africa, and the fact remains that teachers in Africa are being overstressed due to a low manpower. On this note, more empirical research is required to report a real state of things on stress and burnout in Africa.

Conclusions

The preservice teachers' supervisors and in-service teachers' psychological health is of uppermost priority to the educational stakeholders, therefore, since scoping review had shown that more than 99% of the reported participants (teachers) are under stress and at time burnout, increasing the awareness of the research to urgently explore the cause and management of stress and burnout among teachers should be our priority. Furthermore, since the result had indicated that 99% of teachers are under stress and burnout, the fact remains that most of preservice teachers' supervisors are under a serious burnout due to some additional workload attached to their teaching responsibilities as preservice teacher's supervisors. On this note, sponsoring some major research on stress and burnout among the teachers should be an urgent task among educational stakeholders.

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